

INSTITUTIONAL PLANNING AND UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES IN PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN UGANDA

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ABSTRACT

The article reviews the interplay between institutional planning, and unintended consequences in public higher education institutions in Uganda. A desk research design was adopted, in which information was collected from reports, research publications, and online materials. Review of literature revealed the following issues at planning that account for the unintended consequences in higher education institutions; inadequate training of the administrators, planning based on government ideology and policies, complex and unpredictable human behaviour, high financial dependence and inadequate releases of resources to drive institutional mandates. Special attention was paid to the following initiatives; restriction on staff recruitment, informed research and dissemination use, quality assurance and compliance, staff development, and response to uncertainties that are aimed at enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in Higher Education Institutions, however, have resulted in unintended consequences. The following unintended consequences were identified; high workload stress for the academic staff, low quality research output, exposure and aggravation of the social economic inequalities, and declining morale of staff. The article concludes that consequences have repercussions related to the success or failure of an initiative, policy or program of any higher education institution.

It is imperative therefore that higher education institutions periodically evaluate the likely consequences of the decisions made during the planning and budgeting cycle, forecast the possible external and internal factors that are likely to impact on the implementation of their plans and come up with probable risk mitigation and contingency measures for unintended consequences.

Keywords: Institutional Planning, Unintended Consequences, Higher Education Institutions

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1. INTRODUCTION

Effective plans for enhancing quality of higher education are critical if higher education is to produce knowledge, enhance skills and improve human capital development (Trinh, 2023). Development of good plans for higher education requires taking into consideration the prevailing circumstances, the limited resources at their disposal, government policies and the ideology of government, to forecast and attend to unintended consequences (Musaazi, 2013). However, well developed educational plans are sometimes subverted by the manner in which they are implemented leading to unintended consequences taking precedence over the true intent (Brady et al., 2014). This does not only impact on the sustainability of the plans, but on the quality of higher education as well (Beattie et al., 2013).

The development and implementation of plans is explained by the ever changing expectations of the various stakeholders and growing demand for higher education, plus the desire to improve quality of teaching, research and community engagement (Bagoza et al., 2021; Oliver et al., 2019; Musaazi, 2013; Beattie et al., 2013). Occasionally during planning, little attention is paid to the ways in which the interventions may impact either positively or negatively at implementation (Sserugo, 2023; Musaazi, 2013). If the interventions and policies are to succeed, Musaazi (2013) proposes the application of good planning models such as the modern rationality model rather than arriving at decisions in an adhoc manner. The modern rationality planning model entails problem definition, identification of a range of optimal alternatives and testing the alternatives using the model and empirical observations. However, planners of higher education institutions many times find this model of planning inapplicable because they have to plan in reference to the ideology and policies of government (Ovwigho, 1991). In the fear of having their plans rejected by the approving bodies, planners have come up with unrealistic plans that have led to unintended consequences (Kwarteng, 2020). To mitigate the unintended consequences, Ovwigho (2004) calls for the utilization of rational and systematic analysis during planning, taking into consideration the unanticipated obstacles and coming up with mitigation measures for the obstacles.

Planning for higher education is done at two levels; micro and macro levels (Ogunode, 2020). At micro or institutional level, planning includes among others; strategic planning, budgeting, time-tabling, time scheduling, curriculum planning, staff recruitment, research, quality assurance, staff development and response to disasters. At this level, planning requires identification of institutional needs, succinctly stating the problem affecting the institution and the plans of solving the problem, and explicit definition of the method of evaluating results at the implementation of the plan (Ovwigho (1991). It entails careful establishment of priorities and evaluating strategies of achieving them (Ovwigho (1991).

How well or how poorly these priorities are achieved defines performance of an institution (Kaufman, 1972). Whereas at Macro level, planning includes policy making, resource allocation and target setting at state, national and international levels. In this paper, focus is on planning at micro/ institutional level.

The paper focuses on the interplay between institutional planning and unintended consequences in Higher Education Institutions. It is important at this point to define the following key terms in the paper: institutional planning; unintended consequences; and higher education institutions. Dutta, et al. (2019) define institutional planning as the initiation, formulation and implementation of a plan by respective institutions to achieve their predetermined objectives. On the other hand, unintended consequences are unplanned, unexpected outcomes of action oriented toward some goal (Etzioni, 1964). Pryor and Mitchell (2013) define unintended consequences as the unanticipated negative outcomes of planning. Whereas, Burlyuk and Noutcheva (2019) define unintended consequences as “outcomes of purposive action(s) that are not directly intended by an actor”. However, Beattie et al. (2013) assert that unintended consequences may be unforeseen or foreseen and may have positive or negative consequences. In this paper, the unintended consequences refer to negative outcomes of deliberate actions of managers of higher education institutions to enhance quality of higher education. Finally, higher education institutions are those institutions that provide post-secondary education that lead to the award of certificates, diplomas, and degrees (Universities and Other Tertiary Institutions Act, 2001). Obwona and Ssewanyana (2007), cited in Omona (2012), provides examples of higher education institutions as universities, national teachers’ colleges, colleges of commerce and technology, and other schools and colleges, both private and public. Precisely, the institutions include certificate to degree awarding educational institutions. In this paper, higher education institutions mean public universities and other degree awarding institutions.

A desk research design was adopted, in which information was collected from reports, research publications, and online materials. This approach enabled the study to gain a broader outlook and understanding about institutional planning in Higher Education Institutions and, how it leads to unintended consequences. The methodology was found convenient because information in regard to planning in Higher Education institutions was available in academic publications, policy documents, reports and strategic plans on the institutions. Using the critical narrative literature review, the available literature was identified, reviewed, analysed, interpreted and presented. The literature review was conducted on planning and unintended consequences in public Higher Education Institutions.

2. PLANNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Higher Education Institutions implement their mandate through strategic plans that provide unity, and direction of their activities (Kwarteng, 2020). In the case of Uganda, these strategic plans are aligned to the National Development Plan, Vision 2040 and the presidential manifesto (NPA, 2020). For example, Vision 2040 emphasises the critical role of higher education in knowledge production for economic development and enhancement of human capital development which are key ingredients for the transformation of the society from peasant economy to a modern and prosperous country (NPA, 2020). Relatedly, the National Resistance Movement (NRM) presidential manifesto emphasises purposely developing courses in higher education institutions that meet the market demands of the private sector (Media Centre, 2021). The Third National Development Plan (NDPIII) 2020/21 – 2024/25 (NPA, 2020) points out the role of university research in key areas of agriculture, industry production, tourism and digital technology as critical in spurring the country’s economic development (NPA, 2020).

In response to these expectations, Higher Education Institutions in their strategic plans emphasize generating and disseminating cutting edge competence-based knowledge and skills through their three key pillars of teachings, research and community service (Ogunode, 2020). The HEIs have structured the NDP III in their programmes with emphasis on developing the human capital for the enhancement of competitiveness and better quality of life for all.

Information from the review of literature reveals that the strategic plans for higher Education Institutions are set to address the demands of the dynamic external environment (Kwarteng, 2020) and the ever increasing expectations of the various stakeholders plus the competition from other institutions (Zechlin, 2010). Furthermore, to ensure that institutions remain relevant and successful in their endeavours through establishment of the best response mechanisms to changes in the environment (Ovwigbo, 1991), and to enable the administrators to visualise their overall programs in line with the direction of the institutions as they allocate resources in the most efficient manner (Bryson, 2011). The plans are seen to help the various stakeholders of the higher education institutions to understand their tasks and responsibilities and to prepare better for future events given the dynamic external environment (Ovwigbo, 1991).

Several scholars (Kayongo, 2007; Owolabi 2006; Muyimbwa, 2004; Mutula, 2001; Nawe, 2002) attribute success of the strategic plans of Higher Education Institutions to the availability of the financial resources plus effective monitoring and evaluation. Interventions aimed at delivering the desired quality of educational services have to be financially well facilitated as regards their required inputs (Kayongo, 2007; Owolabi 2006). The success of the strategic plans also depends on how well the institutions mobilize the planned resources, utilize these resources as proposed, and also have in place internal control systems (Tam-Wai_Ming, 2008; Musaazi, 2005; Emojorho, 2004). In the same vein, Owolabi (2006) emphasises avoidance of deviations from the planned budget, allocation of resources in a disciplined manner, and efficient utilization of the available resources as ways of minimizing unintended consequences.

Literature reveals incidences of unintended consequences resulting from slip-ups made at the planning stage, implementation stages and/or failure to include the strategic plan priorities in the budget (Zechlin, 2010). Zechlin attributes these unexpected deviations from the plans to failure to adopt high level of flexibility and adjustment of strategies that need to be changed depending on the situation.

3. PLANNING AND UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Information from literature review attributes unintended consequences in the public Higher Education Institutions majorly to availability of finances to operationalise the institutional plans (Kwarteng, 2020). The major source of for these institutions are fees collections from students. The universities rely more on fees collections for their budget rather than diversified sources. Yet, the fees paid by students in the Uganda are less than the unit costs (Nakazzi, 2018). It is estimated that a private student pays only 40% of the annual cost of his/her program (Amutuhaire, 2022). Even with the partial funding of the universities' budgets, government funding of these institutions has dwindled over time despite the growing needs (Basheka & Nabwire, 2013). In response to the decline in government funding, higher education institutions have developed and implemented a number of strategies that negatively impact on their mandate, such as reduced spending on international conferences, community service and stayed the recruitment of new staff (Sserugo, 2023). At implementation stage, some of these strategies have resulted into unintended consequences such as crowded lecture rooms, shortage of instructional resources, low quality research outputs (Hyuha, 2017; Uganda Government, 2020).

Whereas, some scholars (Sserugo, 2023; Kwarteng, 2020; Hyuha, 2017) attribute unintended consequences to adequacy of the allocated resources necessary for the successful implementation of educational plans, Chollete and Harrison (2021) attribute unintended consequences to the complex and unpredictable human behaviour. According to Chollet and Harrison (2021), the intent of the planners may not be attained because those the intervention is meant to serve may not conform to the objectives of the intervention. The non-conformity could be explained by the limitation of resources, inflexibility or bounded rationality. Using bounded rationality, the decision maker will seek for a decision that is good enough rather than the best possible decision. Furthermore, Beattie, et al. (2013) attribute the unintended consequences to the incompetency of most managers of higher education institutions to forecast and manage the unintended outcomes of planning as a result assuming leadership positions without training in planning and budgeting.

4. PRONOUNCED UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Studies reveal unintended consequences in regard to initiatives aimed at enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in Higher Education Institutions, key among which include; restriction on staff recruitment, informed research and dissemination use, quality assurance and compliance, staff development and response to uncertainties (Sserugo, 2023; Bisaso & Achanga, 2023; Kwarteng, 2021; Waruru, 2021; UK Aid, 2019; Beattie et. al, 2013; National Council for Higher Education [NCHE], 2014).

4.1. Restriction on Staff recruitment

Despite the growing enrolment of students in Public Higher Education Institutions, the number of staff has not correspondingly increased. Currently, the staffing in public universities on average fall below 55% (Nakatunde,2019). Notwithstanding the queries by the Auditor General's reports in regard to the shortage of the academic staff, the Ministry of Finance has relegated recruitment and promotion of staff among the unfunded priorities (Monitor, 2021). Understaffing coupled with the growing demand for higher education, and development of new academic programs in addition to the existing ones have resulted in high workload, stress, and inefficiencies for the existing staff (MoFPED, 2018).

To address the shortfall in staffing, Higher Education Institutions have resorted to hiring part-time staff to provide affordable services. Unfortunately, the performance of this category of staff has been rated below expectation (Barifaijo, et al., 2009). The part-time staff hardly participate in administrative work, do not conduct research or engage in community service, they don't attend departmental meetings, their level of absenteeism is high, sometimes they leave without notice even when they have students' work under their assessment (Barifaijo, et al., 2009). Some of the Public Higher Education Institutions have failed to pay the part-time staff for more than ten months (Sserugo, 2023). All these issues compounded together have unintended consequences on the service delivery of the part-time staff.

4.2. Informed Research dissemination and use

Higher Education Institutions are expected to conduct research that generates information that is relevant for policy review and formulation, and that produces new knowledge relevant for social economic development (Kwarteng, 2021). To accomplish this mandate, the institutions have established policies that guide and promote research processes. One of the policies is the inclusion of research publications in the performance appraisal and promotion criteria of the academic staff (National Council for Higher Education [NCHE], 2014).

For example, the academic staff can only be promoted when there is evidence of publication in peer reviewed journals. The unintended consequence of this is that most of the research in the Higher Education Institutions is more of a ritual for academic fulfilment than a response to national and local community needs (Kakembo & Rita, 2017). Currently, the academia in the higher education institutions majorly focus on publishing in academic journals to earn promotions and do not conduct research with the purpose of producing an innovation or product designed for the market (Waruru, 2021). This has left most publications from the developing African countries being so academic and not friendly to the local communities (Waruru, 2021). The unintended consequence is that most of the publications are weak in regard to developing the technology or models for national development (UK Aid, 2019).

4.3. Quality assurance and compliance

A number of plans intended to enhance quality of higher education have become mere rituals and resulted into unintended consequences (Beattie, et al., 2013). Take an example of the student evaluations of teaching a strategy used in several higher education institutions purposely to promote continuous improvement of the teaching practice, support staff management and professional development policies and practices (Villaita-Cerdas, et. al., 2015). The intention of this practice is to help to improve pedagogy, review content, and to assist individual lecturers identify and build on their strengths, and identify and address their weaknesses to National Council for Higher Education [NCHE], 2014). The evaluations are intended to inform interventions to enhance the quality of delivery such as: designing appropriate teaching style and methods, staff training, and identify strong areas that should be sustained (Blair & Noel, 2014). Given that students most times do not have pedagogical knowledge, ability and experience to evaluate the delivery of lecturers, they have tended to rate more lenient lecturers more favourably, and consequently the evaluations are a reflection of the lecturers' popularity rather than quality of delivery (Foster, 2023; Mart, 2017).

4.4. Response to Uncertainties

Higher Education Institutions have plans in regard to dealing with crisis. Unfortunately, the plans for crises are short term. The Covid-19 lockdown of 2020-21 saw schools and HEIs closed as way of managing the spread of Covid-19 pandemic. The lockdown exposed the unpreparedness of higher education institutions for occurrence of disasters such the Covid-19 pandemic (Nawangwe, et al., 2021). HEIs sought for strategies of continuing with the teaching and research supervision. The ODeL mode of delivery was adopted by the HEIs to enable continued teaching and learning with the guidance of NCHE (Bisaso & Achanga, 2023). The adopted e-mode of delivery resulted in lecturers embracing online pedagogy which was a reserve of distance learning. The lecturers who had shunned e-learning models before the pandemic were 'forced' to gain competence in the use of e-learning technology and teaching methods to ensure continued teaching and research supervision. Despite the significant contribution of e-learning to the attainment of set academic targets, the 'forced' adoption of e-learning methodology of delivery had a number of unintended consequences in regard to the motivation and attitude of the lecturers.

The e-learning intervention aggravated the existing social economic inequalities. This mode of delivery was expected to be inclusive and affordable to students in the higher education sector (Bisaso & Achanga, 2023). However, a number of students specifically from the low income background did not benefit from ODEL because of financial constraints to purchase the necessary data for internet connection, some didn't have the required skills to operate e-learning system and some lacked the necessary e-learning amenities (Uzorka & Makeri, 2020). In regard to this, the International Association of Universities (2020) reported that more than 26% students in Africa missed the online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 lockdown.

Overall, the unintended consequence of the adoption of online mode of delivery, is that only a fraction of learners were privileged to access technology continued to learn while others who could not access the necessary technology did not study at all (Nawangwe, et al., 2021). Following these inequities, it is imperative that universities in corroboration with government devise strategies for making e-learning affordable and accessible to all students.

4.5. Staff development

In effort to enhance performance of the academic staff in accordance to the strategic plans, higher education institutions have invested in training their staff to acquire PhDs (Rwothumio, et al., 2021; NCHE, 2014). However, this effort appears not to be bearing results as research and publications remain low, and the contribution of higher education institutions towards national development is not as significant (Rwothumio, et al., 2021). This could be explained by the declining morale of the academic staff who have not been promoted after successfully completing their PhDs (The Observer, July, 2023, 21). The declining morale is manifested by high levels of absenteeism, reduced productivity and problematic interpersonal relations among the staff (Muyiggwa, et al., 2020). These behaviours are unintended consequences that negatively impact on the achievement of the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the institutions. In some incidences, lecturers have moved to other universities where promotions are promptly offered (The Observer, July, 2023, 21). This has created shortfalls in the staffing levels of the institutions.

5. CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD

The aspect of planning informs the future aspirations of an institution to achieve her vision, mission, goals and intended objectives. The failure to involve and consider other key players and external factors during the planning cycle may have repercussions related to the success or failure of an intervention, policy or program. It is imperative for Higher Education Institutions to periodically evaluate the likely consequences of the decisions made during the planning and budgeting cycle, forecast the possible external and internal factors that are likely to impact on the implementation of their plans and come up with probable risk mitigation and contingency measures for unintended consequences. Otherwise, the plans for enhancing quality of higher education will not be achieved and the expectations of the various stakeholders may not be met thus, hindering the contribution of HEIs to National development.

Given that people's attitude are informed by their values and beliefs which influence their reaction to an intervention, it is imperative that the people are consulted to get them carried along before they are committed to the plans (UNESCO, 2013). Higher education institutions should as well carefully plan for the retooling and maintenance of their recruited staff. The retooling should arise from the staff performance issues identified at appraisal level or the need to build capacity as a result of evolving challenges. Furthermore, higher institutions of learning should invest in ICT for e-learning, and should retool their staff in the use of e-learning facilities. Lastly, Government should improve on the existing ICT infrastructure to enhance accessibility of the internet and reduce on the taxes on internet services which in turn will lower the cost of internet services.

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